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Olivo-Cerebello-Nucleo-Olivary Loops Connectivity might be refined during the juvenile multi-innervation Phase of Climbing Fibers onto Purkinje Cells.

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Olivo-Cerebello-Nucleo-Olivary Loops Connectivity might be refined during the juvenile multi-innervation Phase of Climbing Fibers onto Purkinje Cells.

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Abbreviations :

CF	climbing fiber	IO	inferior olive
CN	cerebellar nuclei	LCRT	'Localisation by consistent response time'
CS	conditioned stimulus	LTP/D	long term potentiation/depression
Cx	complex (spike)	MF	mossy fiber
EBR	eye blink reflex	NI	nucleus interpositus
GrL	granular layer	NuC	nuclear cell
HP	hyperpolarization	OCNO	olivo-cerebello-nucleo-olivary
HP-R	hyperpolarization-rebound	PPC	'Privileged partner connection'
		PuC	Purkinje cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

ABSTRACT

In the CN a peculiar asymmetry in the synapsing of PuC axons onto NuCs has been observed : while PuC axons fan out to hundreds of NuCs, the axon terminals can exhibit particularly dense synapsing onto specific NuCs.

It is suggested that such a 'privileged partner connection' (PPC) between PuCs and NuCs only exists when both receive excitation from the same CF, meaning that OCNO-loops are being 'closed' at an almost cellular resolution, hence far more refined than for a closure on the scope of a microzone.

The challenge is : how do PuC axons in the CN recognise the NuCs that were activated by the same CF ?

It can be framed as a 'mapping problem' since any mapping structure that might be present in a CF tract is bound to be scrambled when the fibers fan out to dispersed PuCs of which the axons have to converge back to the CN, and it is in any case a problem for any map that 'loops onto itself'.

It is hypothesized that the CN solves it by forming these PPCs in early life, in the juvenile phase when PuCs are transiently innervated by multiple CFs, and that the phenomenon known as HP-R is instrumental to induce the required LTP and/or synapse budding in the right places.

A program has been written to 'capture' the underlying logic and to 'visualize' the process in action (reproduced here with still images and videorecording). That the desired result can be obtained 'in silico' is a strong argument for that it also can be obtained 'in cerebello'.

It opens quite some functional perspectives if OCNO-loops can 'close' on such a fine resolution, and it also provides explanatory power, e.g. to understand how the CN might deal with conditioned reflexes (like the EBR) – but that in itself is not the subject of this article.

INTRODUCTION

Sensory afferents often gather together in a fiber tract in such an orderly fashion that the spatial interfiber relationships by themselves carry information content : a map. It is of cardinal importance that higher centers can process information on a level of resolution as refined as it is collected on the sensory input side.

Maps can be very diverse : they can represent a surface (a body map), or a succession of parameter values (e.g. a frequency map), they can be anything besides sensory, and efferents can be mapped too.

We trust fiber tracts not to scramble their internal ordering (their fiber parallelism) and trust chemotaxis to guide them precisely to their targets during ontogeny (and maybe later too) .

Maps can be 'handed over' to a next fiber tract (allowing for e.g. lateral inhibition while doing it), or they can be projected onto a 'processing field' like in the cortices.

In the cerebellum MFs bring in a plethora of mapped signals, and they are all projected onto the GrL, above which the PuCs are positioned, being 'mapped' too in this way.

MF collaterals project onto NuCs in the CN but it remains to be seen if 'collateralizing' can produce a fiber tract that preserves the mapping of the main tract....

CFs directly target PuCs while their collaterals directly target NuCs and as a rule (exceptions exist) they 'map' onto the microzonal organisation.

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“The climbing fiber projections to the cerebellar cortex are arranged topographically in those specific narrow sagittal bands (Brodal et al., 1975; Courville, 1975; Brodal, 1976; Chan-Palay et al., 1977; Wiklund et al., 1984) and follow the zebrin expression pattern in the cerebellar cortex (Sugihara and Shinoda, 2004).”

“This spatial configuration of inputs within a circumscribed region of the cerebellar nuclei suggests a global organization of the cerebellum in small units where a confined area of the inferior olive projects to a segregated strip of Purkinje cells in the cerebellar cortex and to a given part of the cerebellar nuclei which receive from this specific band of cortex. In turn, this area of the cerebellar nucleus is innervating the inferior olive sub-nucleus from which it is receiving. This organization in reciprocal loops implements a modular organization of the cerebellum.”

Yet, we still could call that a 'coarse resolution' mapping (connecting whole microzones with specific regions in the CN), but we should envisage the possibility of a finer resolution mapping on the level of individual cells or small clusters of them - and then we can wonder if the CF tract targeting a microzone - on this resolution - carries a map or maps like MF tracts can.

The absence of map content, however, does not preclude the existence of a 'structural' map if fiber tracts keep respecting their internal fiber ordering and can hand it over to the following stages : we might speak of 'empty maps' or 'homogeneous maps' in these cases (a 'featureless' map, not representing different parameter values) .

However, as for the collaterals of MFs onto the CN, it remains to be seen if CF collaterals onto the CN are able to preserve the main fiber map.

When all NuCs in a subregion of a CN (say the EBR region of the NI) are dedicated in unison to the same effector, then CF mapping of finer resolution is in principle not necessary (any PuC group of the microzone may engage any NuC group and the effect is grossly the same), and yet - if a structural albeit homogeneous map is present - the potentiality arises that a specific PuC group is to engage a specific NuC group.

Considering the setup of the microzone, it seems reasonable to say that 'democracy' demands that all PuCs of the microzone must be able to bring in their share in determining the output of the NuC subregion, and hence PuCs should pool and distribute their output in this NI subregion by massive convergence and divergence of their axon terminals.

[2] (Uusisaari et al. 2011)

“In vivo, large individual IPSPs are rare, at least in the presumed large glutamatergic projection neurons (Bengtsson et al. 2008). This lack of significant fluctuations suggests that large projection neurons are the target of a large number of equally contributing, for the most time non-synchronized PNs that jointly evoke thousands of inhibitory postsynaptic events per second.”

That is what effectively happens : when entering the CN, PuC axons branch extensively insofar that one NuC is contacted by hundreds of PuCs, but - alas - by doing so, they destroy any map content that they might have been carrying in their fiber tract structure.

[2] (Uusisaari et al. 2011)

“It seems clear that there must be substantial convergence of the cortico-nuclear pathways. If the convergence was equal over all CN and CN cell types, and each PN would be assumed to innervate only a single postsynaptic target, one would expect in the order

of 20 PNs converging on a single CN neuron. A PN axon is, however, known to branch extensively within their conical target fields, within which several tens of large CN neuron cell bodies or dendritic segments are estimated to fit.”

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“Furthermore, different Purkinje cells converge onto the same nuclear cell. Palkovits and colleagues (Palkovits et al., 1977) initially evoked a convergence of 860 Purkinje cells upon a single nuclear cell by counting the number of terminals ending onto it. However, this number was reevaluated in recent studies (Person and Raman, 2012a), bringing back this ratio to 30-50 Purkinje cells per nuclear cell.”

But even without the final map-spoiling divergence of the PuC terminals, targeted 'delivery' of PuC output onto NuCs would be extremely problematic, by the fact that it is as good as impossible for a map that loops onto itself to 'reconnect' correctly.

Indeed, handing over a map from one fiber tract to the next one only requires appositioning of their surfaces, allowing each fiber to contact a partner on the other side, but when a map is looped onto itself each terminal fiber has to detect the original fiber with the same 'coordinates' on the map surface.

Such a detailed point-to-point reconnection not only requires precise appositioning of the surfaces, but also correct appositioning of all points on the surface, and the slightest relative rotational deviation of the fiber tracts will spoil that.

If you don't use electrical cable connectors which are physically designed to be asymmetrical to prevent connection errors, then you risk trouble when an electrical device e.g. needs DC (direct current) or grounding (note that you can connect extension cables without worrying about their orientation, but you have to test the terminal plug outputs before connecting the device to ascertain yourself of the correct plug orientation).

Plug asymmetry of course will not be the cerebellar strategy to connect a tract containing thousands of fibers to the next one in order to keep track of the correct map orientation.

It is difficult to conceive that – on this fine resolution – chemotaxis would be capable of closing loops on NuCs connected to the same CFs that excited the PuCs which return their axons to them. We must assume that it is done by functional ways since on this resolution NuCs (of same type) are chemically/genetically identical.

An indication that the CN solves it can be seen in the curious asymmetrical pattern of synapse formation displayed in it : PuC axon terminals synapse very strongly on some NuCs, and very weakly on all the others.

[2] (Uusisaari et al. 2011)

“It is known that a single PN axon can form as many as 50 on some and as few as one synaptic terminal on other target neurons (Palkovits et al. 1977), suggesting that even though a CN cell could be contacted by a large number of individual presynaptic PNs, most of the synaptic terminals could be formed by axonal branches from just a few (3–4) presynaptic PNs with tens of presynaptic terminals each.”

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“Within the nuclei, a Purkinje cell axon contacts primarily 3 to 6 principal neurons on their somata while providing weak input to many more (Palkovits et al., 1977) .”

It suggests the following strategy :

All PuCs synapse weakly on a lot of NuCs to pool and distribute the output that is to affect the effector (e.g. of the EBR ...) , but at the same time each PuC singles out the NuC (group) that receives the (collaterals of the) CF that fired the PuC itself and on which it is to synapse heavily.

Reworded : PuCs form PPCs with NuCs when sharing the same CF, but keep in touch with many others.

How is it done ?

METHOD

A demo program was written in Visual FoxPro 9.0 to display graphically and dynamically the hypothesized formation of PPCs in the CN. Several considerations inferred from observations made ‘in cerebello’ are ‘translated’ into code and parameters were tuned until the desired result was achieved, thereby proving the ‘feasibility’ of it ‘in silico’ and providing insights in the process as well.

In this article screenshots (‘still images’) and videolinks (clickable in the PDF file) are used to render the demo.

SETTING THE STAGE

The demo depicts the situation as in Fig. 1A :

Fig. 1A

CFs (and their collaterals) are shown in yellow, PuC axons in blue (PuCs themselves are not depicted), NuCs are represented by green dots and are connected each to a specific CF collateral on their left side, while terminal PuC axon branches (in black) fan out and connect to all NuCs on their right side.

For simplicity of display a one-to-one CF-PuC connection is assumed (in vivo CFs contact 1 to 10 PuCs) : but you may view the PuCs as groups of PuCs (united by a common CF) . Idem dito for the CF-NuC connection : NuCs may also receive more than one CF, but it will not matter for the demonstration of the principle.

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“A single olivo-cerebellar axon gives rise to several collaterals (up to six) which innervate only one given cerebellar nucleus (Sugihara et al., 1996, 1999) although territories covered by each nuclear collateral are only partially overlapping (Sugihara et al., 1996) .Therefore, innervation from climbing fibers appears to be more circumscribed than mossy fiber inputs.”

“No one-to-one relationship between climbing fibers and nuclear neurons was found as in the cerebellar cortex (Audinat et al., 1992) . Instead, several different climbing fibers appear to converge onto the same nuclear neurons, even though clear anatomical evidence of multiple innervations of the principal neurons by olivo-cerebellar fibers is still lacking.”

It is also left in the middle here which type of NuCs are involved.

Fig. 1A is to develop into a desired end situation as shown in Fig. 1B, the thick PuC axon terminal lines representing heavy LTP'd (or dense – it is considered to be equivalent) synapsing onto the NuC.

'Scrambling' of fiber parallelism is depicted by lines of which the positions are shuffled, and in that case begin and desired end situations are as in Fig. 2A and 2B.

Fig. 1B

Fig. 2A

Fig. 2B

The thick PuC axon branches are the 'privileged ones' and they connect with the NuC that received excitation from the CF that fired the same PuC (look at the indexes).

With or without scrambling, the problem of how to implement a transition from A to B is the same in both situations since it is in any case a 'looping map reconnection problem'.

THE ASSOCIATION PROBLEM

Fig. 3

Let's activate one CF 'in silico' : the activated circuit is shown in red, and one of the PuC terminals finds the partner NuC on which CF-NuC synapses are activated.

We are going to assume that - if this occurs - LTP is induced at the PuC-NuC synapse (with the NuC subjected to PuC-NuC LTP shown in yellow) .

LTP induction in the CN is no simple matter however : it cannot rely on the co-occurrences of presynaptic stimulations and postsynaptic depolarizations since these are constantly triggered in the CN by 'intrinsic firing', and that precludes the assignment of any 'associative' value to it by continually generating 'false coincidences'.

[3] (Pugh et al. 2009) (Ref in context of MF to NuC LTP, but considered valid for PuC axon to NuC LTP as well).
 "Because of spontaneous firing, any mossy-fiber-dependent excitatory postsynaptic currents (EPSPs) has a reasonable chance of overlapping temporally with an action potential in a nuclear cell. Therefore, the Hebbian condition of correlated pre- and postsynaptic spiking arises randomly, which is predicted to yield a noisy signal."

"In the deep cerebellar nuclei, Hebbian patterns of coincident synaptic excitation and postsynaptic firing fail to induce long-term increases in the strength of excitatory inputs."

“Such results indicate that circuits with intrinsically active neurons have rules for information transfer and storage that distinguish them from other brain regions.”

PuC triggered NuC HP-R is used as a more reliable condition for the induction of LTP.

There is also the problem that PuCs are inhibiting neurons and hence normally do not cause a depolarization. The HP-R phenomenon solves it all : it turns HP into ‘rebound’ (depolarization) and as an event it rises above the background of the intrinsic firing.

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“During the rebound, the increased excitability and associated spike burst induce large intracellular calcium transients in the principal neurons (Aizenman et al., 1998; Zhang et al., 2004; Schneider et al., 2013). By this way, inhibitory Purkinje cell inputs can drive postsynaptic excitation and calcium entry in the nuclear neurons, which mechanism may be the basis for plasticity at the Purkinje cell to principal neurons synapse (Aizenman et al., 1998).”

THE DURATION PROBLEM

HP-R brings in problems of its own by

- 1) **needing some time to build up ...**

[4] (De Zeeuw et al. 2011)

“Complex spikes are transmitted as small bursts of action potentials down the Purkinje cell axon and evoke profound inhibitory postsynaptic potentials (IPSPs) in the target neurons in the cerebellar and vestibular nuclei. After the inhibition, which can last for tens of milliseconds, the nucleus neurons can show a profound increase in firing, known as rebound firing.”

requiring activated CF-NuC synapses to trigger a cascade that ‘keeps the memory of their activation alive’ until the depolarisation occurs.

[3] (Pugh et al. 2009)

“Synaptic excitation must occur in a specific time window to induce potentiation, preceding the hyperpolarization and rebound by no more than a few hundred milliseconds.”

- 2) **and by being a cell-wide phenomenon, requiring activated PuC-NuC synapses to do the same as to stay ‘tagged’ as the specific locations where LTP is to take place.**

[3] (Pugh et al. 2009)

“The hyperpolarization and/or rebound provide a global signal (possibly by modulating CaMKII) that enables potentiation to proceed only at previously marked synapses.”

Hence : if a particular CF fires and if some 400 ms later the CF-affected NuC group is subjected to HP-R, then the involved PuC-NuC synapses potentiate.

[5] (Pugh et al. 2008)

“We find that the extent of plasticity varies with the relative timing of synaptic excitation and hyperpolarization. Potentiation is most effective when synaptic stimuli precede the postinhibitory rebound by ~400 ms, whereas with longer intervals, or with a reverse sequence, EPSCs tend to depress.”

THE INTERFERENCE PROBLEM

As far as the demo program is concerned LTP can be considered to occur when both CF and PuC terminal ‘activate’ the same NuC, but we have to keep the 400 ms time lapse in mind, since it can hardly be looked upon as a ‘coincidence detection’.

400 ms is awfully long when in the meantime all CFs onto the region are regularly firing with 1 to 10 Hz, causing all their ‘partner’ PuCs to send Cx spikes onto the CN, all NuCs seeing PuC activity coming in from all sides.

Let’s – in a first demo run – assume that there is no such interference i.e. CF firing is always followed by HP-R and this sequence is always completed before a next sequence is triggered.

Under these conditions we see an uncomplicated emergence of PuC-NuC LTP by the thickening of the specific PuC axon terminal branch that connects to the NuC which was depolarized by the same CF as the PuC (with LTP assumed to saturate at a certain level to prevent runaway), cfr Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 , videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/waslr5ed6iem9rb/demo-2-5.mp4?dl=0>

It 'reconnects' NuC-PuC partners regardless of the scrambling of the CF-map.

The strategy is remotely reminiscent of a 'ping-test' [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ping_\(networking_utility\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ping_(networking_utility)) : here the CF-activated NuC 'listens' for a response of a PuC to arrive in a certain latency window, and when it does 'concludes' it must be its partner to which it has to LTP the connection with : we might call it a 'localisation by consistent response time' (LCRT) process.

The critical factor for the LCRT process, however, is the 'separateness' : if a non-related PuC by chance also happens to give a 'response' in the time window that a NuC is 'listening', then this NuC will mistake the PuC to be a partner while it is not (not activated by the same CF that activated the NuC).

Ideally the LCRT windows should not overlap, but probably there is some tolerance for as long as the 'right partners' respond more frequently in the concerned time-window than the 'false partners' do (and this announces already the need for LTD to undo 'spurious' LTP) : specialists in stochastics may calculate the limits of it.

In vivo, the bombardment of CF firing surely seems to preclude this strategy, but it is also observed that single Cx spikes are not powerful enough to cause HP-R : only with enough synchrony of PuCs can it be obtained.

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“This control of the nuclear neurons activity by the Purkinje cell inputs have been shown to be critical for motor control (Witter et al., 2013), notably by the fact that the principal neurons can elicit rebound firing after a profound hyperpolarization followed by a release of the inhibition. One good candidate mechanism for such input pattern is given by the climbing fiber activity and its ensuing synchronization of the Purkinje cell complex spikes.”

“If concomitantly synchronized Purkinje cells within the same sagittal band converge their axons upon the same nuclear neurons, this phenomenon would be largely amplified and thus sufficient to provide inhibition onto principal neurons to deactivate the T-type channels and to trigger the rebound firing. Rebound discharge of the nuclear neurons indeed appears after inferior olive activation (Rowland and Jaeger, 2008; Hoebeek et al., 2010; Bengtsson et al., 2011).”

The frequency of a synchronized event as counted over the region however drops with its scale and will go way below the frequency of single Cx spike events.

It becomes interesting when - on average - this frequency is so low that 400 ms can elapse before it happens again, recreating the condition that is needed to have 'CF-firing HP-R sequences' that can terminate without interference by other instantiated sequences.

However, when LTP is not yet realized at the PuC-NuC synapses, much ampler synchronous PuC Cx spike firing is needed to generate HP of significance, presuming that a single CF connected to say 10 PuCs will still be insufficient.

Larger groups of PuCs should fire in synchrony (or in a small time window), and we can speculate on how this might be realised.

[6] (Wise et al. 2010)

“Synchrony in complex spike activity is thought to be due to one (or a weighted combination) of three mechanisms :
- climbing fibre branching (Armstrong et al. 1973a,b,c; Sugihara et al. 1995);
- electrotonic coupling between olive cells (e.g. Llinas et al. 1974);
- and/or synchronous afferent input driving activity in common groups of olive cells.”

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“Two types of spontaneous IPSCs/IPSPs have been recorded from CN principal neurons in vivo (Bengtsson et al., 2011; Witter et al., 2013): a barrage of low-amplitude and high-frequency synaptic events reflecting the spontaneous firing of presynaptic PCs (Person and Raman, 2012a), and giant low-frequency IPSC/Ps. Giant IPSC/Ps have been proposed to result from the synchronization of PCs by climbing fibers (Bengtsson et al., 2011; Person and Raman, 2012b; Witter et al., 2013).”

“Indeed, large IPSCs are readily evoked during tactile stimulations of the cutaneous climbing fiber receptive field (Bengtsson and Jörntell, 2014) and by electrical stimulations of the inferior olive (Hoebeek et al., 2010; Bengtsson et al., 2011), driving powerful rebound firing of the CN cells which induces plasticity at CN synapses (Aizenman et al., 1998; Pugh and Raman, 2006).”

The IO is in a position to ‘organize’ synchrony, enabling a large group of PuCs - by pooling their Cx spike output - to reach the threshold to provoke LTP triggering HP-R.

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“This parasagittal organization of the climbing fiber cortical inputs has important consequences on the Purkinje cell activity within and across the longitudinal bands thereby defined. A circumscribed subdivision of the inferior olive innervates many Purkinje cells within a longitudinal zone, and the activation of this beam of climbing fibers thus induces synchronized complex spikes within this parasagittal band of Purkinje cells, with millisecond precision (Welsh et al., 1995; Hanson et al., 2000; Ozden et al., 2009; Schultz et al., 2009; Wise et al., 2010).”

Synchronized PuC activity might also originate in the PuC layer itself by common MF stimulation, but the absence of concomitant CF firing at the CN might prevent HP to become HP-R.

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

After sensory stimulation, the responses of nuclear neurons in vivo do not present the expected rebound discharge after inhibition periods, but rather consist in a sequence of early excitation – intermediate inhibition – late increase in firing rate (Armstrong et al., 1975; Rowland and Jaeger, 2005).”

With synchronized CF firing however, large groups of PuCs will HP-R large groups of 'primed' NuCs, and this will generate too much widespread LTP (creating a lot of 'false partnerships') .

With LTP growing in force though, a moment will be reached when a somewhat smaller PuC group can HP-R a somewhat smaller NuC group - requiring less CFs to fire in synchrony, and some LTP'd synapses that now find themselves in a situation that HP-R is not accompanied with CF-NuC synapse activation will start to undergo LTD - since this plasticity rule is to be added as an obligatory component (refs again in context of MFs) .

[1] (Husson et al. 2014)

“Crucial involvement of the inhibition upon nuclear neurons was confirmed by studies investigating long-term plasticity at the mossy fiber to nuclear neuron synapses. This synapse is potentiated when presynaptic high-frequency bursts of EPSPs precede a post-inhibitory rebound by 400 milliseconds (Pugh and Raman, 2006, 2008) . If the EPSPs burst is not followed by a hyperpolarization period or instead precede a depolarization of the soma (Zhang and Linden, 2006), or if the inhibition appears after 400 milliseconds or before the excitation (Pugh and Raman, 2006, 2008), the synapse is depressed.”

“Timing of the mossy fiber collateral inputs onto nuclear neurons with respect to the occurrence of a rebound induced by the Purkinje cells inhibition is crucial for the directionality of the synaptic plasticity. This may suggest that whenever the Purkinje cells inputs is occurring at the right interval with the direct collaterals inputs onto the nuclear neurons, these excitatory inputs are selected and strengthened to improve the spiking output of the cerebellar nuclei (De Zeeuw et al., 2011) .”

It is a resolution refining process that continues until the degree of divergence of CFs onto NuCs puts a limit to it.

When the process is stabilized, each NuC (group) is heavily connected to its partner PuC (group) with which it shares CF inputs and hence can be HP-R'd by this same PuC (group) alone, but each NuC (group) also remains weakly connected to all the other PuCs which by their number are capable of transmitting the pooled PuC signal to it.

It implies that LTD may never be able to 'kill' a PuC-NuC connection, and the LTP process itself should also be limited by a saturation ceiling.

In the next demo run, the initial requirement will be that 10 PuCs have to join forces (being activated by 10 CFs), and when LTP is sufficiently incremented to guarantee that 10-1 PuCs can do the job, the group size is decremented (and so on).

Since the program is bound to be serial in execution, 'synchrony' will be simulated by a summing process of the 'effort' of each PuC, at the end of which the resulting total is compared to a 'threshold' to determine if LTP is to ensue.

As already mentioned, - in vivo - it probably is only HP that results in a rebound that triggers LTP while just HP triggers LTD (CF excitation at the NuC making the difference).

LTD will come to a halt since LTD diminishes the amplitude of the HP which – at a certain moment – becomes incapable of inducing still more LTD, and hence it protects the 'non-partner' NuC-PuC connections from being 'killed' altogether : it is mandatory that they stay 'alive' to enable PuCs to pool their output and send it to all NuCs.

Have a look at how it 'unrolls' and watch the initial 'flooding by LTP' and the ensuing 'cleaning up' by LTD until single PuCs finally connect to single NuCs (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 , videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/1cnjuk65q21t74h/demo-2-6.mp4?dl=0>

A peculiar aspect of the scenario here is that CFs must 'join forces' to start with, but must cease to do so gradually with the passage of time, and never may return to the CF-based synchronized mode of firing (of that scope).

Could that be programmed by the IO ?

It is striking however that during the early postnatal days there is a period in which PuCs first are contacted by multiple CFs, and that a kind of competing contest ensues which comes to an end when a PuC is only targeted by one CF (but one CF may still target 1 to 10 PuCs).

[7] (Whitney et al. 2009)

“In the developing rodent cerebellum, a single PC is innervated by multiple climbing fibers (Mariani and Changeux, 1981; Crepel, 1982; Kakizawa et al., 2000) . As the rodent cerebellum matures, however, surplus climbing fibers regress and, by the second to third postnatal week, a time that corresponds to the final few weeks of human gestation (Bayer et al., 1993), each PC is innervated by a single climbing fiber (Mariani and Changeux, 1981; Kano et al., 1997; Hashimoto and Kano, 2005).”

Assuming that it is not the ratio of NuC to PuC numbers that is changing, it must mean that single CFs start by innervating a lot more PuCs than just 1 to 10 : with 5 CFs/PuC, single CFs would innervate 5 to 50 PuCs.

With each CF causing a larger group of PuCs to fire in unison, we get in essence the same situation as when clusters of CFs fire in unison, and the demo program was adapted to include this altered scenario in which - at the start - each CF activates one NuC but ten PuCs, and then gradually sees the number of PuCs 'under its control' dwindling to just one. Have a look (Fig. 6) :

Fig. 6 , videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/bx1vjhlrhr2dlx2/demo-2-7.mp4?dl=0>

It seems that a period of CF-boostered PuC synchronizing is necessary to provide for HP-R and LTP in a situation where synapses are weak to begin with, but in doing so the 'separation requirement' is violated (HP-R being no rare event any more and occurring frequently during a 400 ms time lapse), the interferences causing an 'overflow' of LTP and the unbridled formation of 'false' PPCs.

Having arrived in a situation where many synapses are heavily LTP'd however, the decline in synchronicity scope allows for a 'pruning' of these false PPCs (though not killing them) by LTD, while keeping the real PPCs in full strength.

TUNING

In-program, a number of parameters had to be properly tuned to arrive successfully at PPC formation : not every combination of settings will give a 'desired' result.

Obviously, the LTP threshold (when HP can result in rebound) must be set way higher than the LTD threshold (under which HP is too weak to provoke LTD), and LTP step must be > LTD step, to give LTP a chance to bring synapses to saturation, but with how much difference ?

In the 'group activation' demos LTP and LTD compete, and when LTP is not way stronger than LTD, some NuCs do not succeed in 'finding their partner' and - worse - 'false partnerships' may remain or even prevail.

Two examples of a connection process going astray are shown in Fig. 7 : execution was stopped after 100000 steps since the procedure could not recover from the situation in which it found itself stuck.

Fig. 7 , videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/bpfyi6i6bwy31oo/demo-2-9l.mp4?dl=0>

We can ask ourselves what it means physiologically when a stage has to be gone through in which there is a general PuC-NuC synapse saturation over the whole NuC population - and if that matters in the early postnatal days.

In vivo, many other factors might be changing in these critical postnatal days : the strength and number of CF-PuC synapses, the firing sensitivity of PuCs, the thresholds for LTP and LTD in the CN, and concerted changes in all these parameters might be used to steer the process smoothly in the right direction.

[8] (Van Welie et al. 2011)

See figures 1 and 2 on page 2 of "The metamorphosis of the developing cerebellar microcircuit".

"We suggest that these transient features may set circuit activity, regulate synaptic plasticity, and alter network connectivity, and that these transient features may be pivotal in the developing circuit to guide the emergence of the mature cerebellum."

CONCLUSION

Demonstrating the feasibility of PPCs in silico is no proof that PPCs are formed in cerebello, but it provides a strong argument for it. Of course, actual research is to corroborate or to falsify this hypothesis.

Other arguments are that it 'gives sense' to the observation of gross asymmetric synapsing of PuCs onto NuCs, and to the juvenile phase of CF multi-innervation onto PuCs.

It is a complicated process since it has to circumvent the presence of intrinsic firing, must be based on phenomena which only Cx spikes can provoke (since only CF related activity is to be associated), and has to find a way to turn inhibition into depolarization.

The HP-R phenomenon solves it, but in turn it introduces an interference problem due to its long duration and due to the requirement of having to engage large groups of PuCs to fire Cx spikes in synchrony to provoke HP-R when LTP is still minimal.

This problem is then to be solved by the decrementing CF innervation phase in early life, which enforces widespread LTP by brute force to begin with, and then allows for 'a release of the LTP-lock' by LTD'ing those NuC-PuC pairs which loose their 'privilege' of being partners by the reduction in CF connectivity, causing them to share no common CF any more.

It finally results in having NuCs which can only be HP-R'd by the sole force of their partner PuCs, thanks to the massively LTP'd PuC-NuC synapses (or/and by the amount of them), and the continuing HP-R'ing 'locks' them in this connectivity status.

They keep in touch though with many other PuCs for the modulation of their normal firing.

Synchronization of PuCs by MFs does not result in HP-R, and synchronization by CF firing is supposed to be incapable of causing HP-R through non-LTP'd synapses in non-partner NuCs when the CF multi-innervation phase is over.

Hence the non-partner connectivity status should also remain stable for life.

All this concerns the CFs, the connectivity of NuCs with MF collaterals is another story (and the many citations 'in the context of' MFs instead of CFs vouch for it).

DISCUSSION

While the proposed mechanism for their formation is speculative, let's nonetheless accept for a moment that PPCs are built in the CN between PuCs and NuCs that share a common CF, a feat that might have been taken for granted in many a simulation.

If PuC axons can localize the partner NuC in the CN then a point-to-point reconnection of a CF map looping onto itself has been realized, even if the map were scrambled by loosing fiber parallelism in the CF or PuC axon tracts. It makes the necessity for structural conservation of mapping (by parallelism of fibers) obsolete, i.e. at this finer resolution.

While 'OCNO-loop philosophy' only requires that the cortical microzone which is 'alerted' by CFs should return its output to the population of NuCs that was synchronously alerted by the collaterals of these same CFs, PPCs would refine the resolution of the closure of these loops almost to the level of individual PuC-NuC partners.

I would suggest to refer to the 'tiny OCNO loops' - created through PPC formation - as 'nanoloops'.

Having a fine resolution of OCNO nanoloops inside a microzone allows for task diversification along a supplementary dimension, say when an MF map is projected onto the population of nanoloops.

In the CN, receiving MF collaterals, it might allow for the segregated processing of different points (or small subregions) in this map by dedicated nanoloop groups.

More specifically, when considering the EBR and the NI, it offers ‘explanation avenues’ as to how the NI might deal with different CS modalities when they trigger the ‘same’ EBR. Note that a CS modality interference problem (cross-modal transfer) is observed in the juvenile CF multi-innervation period, which gradually disappears ... with the formation of the PPCs ?

[9] (Brown et al. 2008)

“Evidence of cross-modal transfer of ISI-specific response features has been demonstrated in our laboratory using a version of the differential conditioning procedure employed in rabbit EBC (Green Steinmetz, 2005; Kehoe et al., 1989 - Experiment 3; Kehoe, Horne, Horne, 1993; Mauk Ruiz, 1992) that we have adapted for rats (Brown, Pagani, Stanton, 2006) .

In this “ISI discrimination” task, subjects are trained in a delay EBC procedure using within-sessions presentations of two distinct CSs – one CS (e.g., tone) is conditioned at a short ISI (280 ms) and the other CS (e.g., light) is conditioned at a long ISI (880 ms) .

When training commences at PD23 or 30, conditioning to the long CS is strongly influenced by the short CS-US pairing, as evidenced by earlier peak latencies, enhanced CR amplitudes, and increased frequency of double-peaked CRs to the long CS relative to controls that do not receive paired short CS-US presentations.

However, ISI discrimination performance in adults (PD80+ at the start of training; Brown et al. – Experiment 3) does not demonstrate the magnitude of influence of short ISI conditioning upon performance to the long CS observed in younger subjects.

Enhanced cross-modal transfer from the short to long CS in ISI discrimination diminishes – and temporal precision of CRs to the long CS improves between (approximately) PD30-80.”

“While crossmodal transfer has been documented across multiple species, age ranges, and conditioning procedures (Campolattaro Freeman, 2006; Duong, Brown, Stanton, 2007; Frieman Goyette, 1973; Kehoe Holt; Molina et al.; Spear and Molina; Thomas, Miller, & Svinicki, 1971), the neurobiological mechanisms underlying ontogenetic changes in this phenomenon are currently unknown.”

In the cortex cerebelli, MF projections might also ‘parcellate’ a microzone and be processed differentially. Here it is to be noted that a collateralizing CF targets quite separated points in the elongated parasagittal strip of a microzone and hence it looks as if a nanoloop is going to ‘engage’ 1 to 10 non-adjacent (!) points of an MF map projected onto the GrL underneath the PuCs.

[10] (Pijpers et al. 2006)

“The climbing fiber collaterals were distributed to the paravermal cerebellum as continuous strips or, occasionally, as isolated patches that fell within a longitudinal band of cortex that was aligned with the injection site (Fig. 2A, shown in black, arrow) . More specifically, from the injection site caudalward, labeled climbing fibers were noted in the caudal one-half of PMD (lobule VII) and rostralward in crus 2b, crus 1a, SL, and caudal one-half of lobule V .”

Since the PuCs belonging to a nanoloop are dispersed, I would refrain from saying that a microzone contains ‘nanozones’ but nonetheless, it is functionally to be interpreted as a parcellation of a microzone : a particular nanoloop seems ‘to take a pick of PuCs’ in disparate patches of the microzone.

However, it is surprising that MFs are observed to collateralize over a microzone in register with the CFs.

A particular collateralizing MF targets the same PuCs (i.e. the GrL spots underneath them) as a particular collateralizing CF does and they even do the same when the CFs contact more than one microzone in the case of microcomplexes.

[10] (Pijpers et al. 2006)

“Labeled climbing fiber collaterals were distributed as longitudinal strips and were always accompanied by clusters of labeled mossy fiber rosettes in the subjacent granular layer.”

“The mossy fiber system makes use of highly organized projection patterns that relate closely to the topography of the climbing fiber system.”

“The correspondence between the distribution of climbing fiber collaterals and mossy fiber collaterals is striking.”

“Two- and three-dimensional reconstructions and quantitative analysis showed that mossy fibers also collateralized to other stripe-like regions usually below Purkinje cells with the same zebrin-positive or zebrin-negative characteristics as that of the injection site and associated climbing fiber collaterals.”

“These data indicate that nonadjacent cerebellar zones, sharing the same climbing fiber input and zebrin identity, also share a common mossy fiber input. Other cerebellar cortical regions that receive collaterals from the same mossy fibers usually also have the same zebrin signature.”

[11] (Apps et al. 2009)

“An increasing body of evidence points to an alignment (anatomical and physiological) between mossy fibre and climbing fibre projections that target the same Purkinje cell stripes.”

“Mossy fibre terminations are in register with regions of the cerebellar cortex that are defined by their climbing fibre input from different body parts rather than with longitudinal zones per se.”

“Wherever climbing fibre terminals were located in the cortex, labelled mossy fibre terminals were situated in the underlying granular layer. Moreover, labelled mossy fibre terminals were also located in other parts of the cortex, immediately below Purkinje cell stripes with the same zebrin II phenotype as the longitudinal zone under study.”

It is an indication that MF projections onto the cortex cerebelli ‘want’ to hand over an intact map onto the nanoloop system of PPCs, and this may be of great functional relevance.

Miscellaneous remarks :

- We may wonder if the strategy of LCRT is used in other regions of the brain, since it is baffling how often there are high degrees of axonal arborisation / divergence in nuclei, raising the question how that can nonetheless ultimately result in very precise functional output.

[12] (Apps et al. 2018)

“Between all these different targets, such as thalamus and medullary reticular formation, profuse collateralization of nuclear efferents is observed. In this respect, it is hard to understand how this system of diverging and partly converging connections is being used in an integrated way to result in coordinated learning and execution of movements, cognitive and affective behavior, or visceral functions.”

- It should be noted that in places where a map is scrambled but 'reconnected' by PPCs, there is still a map, but it might be more or less invisible to anatomical scrutiny (cfr Voogd, concerning Deiters' nucleus, and it seems to suggest also that PPC formation could span several microzones) .

[13] (Voogd et al. 2016)

“The medio-lateral somatotopical organization of the B zone was confirmed and extended by Andersson and Oscarsson.

They recorded climbing fiber potentials from Purkinje cells of the B zone and found a regular arrangement of long, narrow “microzones” containing Purkinje cells that receive their climbing fiber input from the same receptive fields.

Responses on stimulation of hindlimb nerves are located in the lateralmost microzone, purely forelimb in a medial microzone and different combinations in the intermediate three microzones. Each of these microzones projects to a particular population of neurons in Deiters' nucleus. These neurons are intermingled in the nucleus, with the hindlimb population predominating in its caudal part. The somatotopical organization of the nucleus, apparently, is not as precise as maintained by Pompeiano and Brodal.”

- The demo is very ‘schematic’ : 10 NuCs, 10 PuCs, all connected and ‘defining’ a region in the CN related to a microzone. PPC formation can only go as far as PuC axons can fan out to reach as many NuCs as possible. When the ‘partner NuC’ (the one activated by the same CF) is ‘out of reach’ then a PPC cannot be formed. It sets a limit to the extend of the scrambling which can be tolerated in the CF tract and the PuC axon tract.

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